

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <http://www.researchgate.net/publication/285482784>

Critical Factors in Competitive Advantage of Islamic Banking

CONFERENCE PAPER · OCTOBER 2015

2 AUTHORS, INCLUDING:

[Al, R. Firend](#)

Universiti Teknologi Malaysia

19 PUBLICATIONS 0 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

INTAC VI

**6th IIUM International Accounting Conference
28 - 29 October 2015, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia**

SESSION 2 D - Theme: Management Accounting

Chairperson: Prof. Dr. Shamsul Nahar Abdullah

Time: 09.00 am – 10.30 am

Venue: Seminar Room F Level 2

Title	Presenter(s)/Author(s)
1- Critical Factors in Competitive Advantage of Islamic Banking	Firend Al. R., Maryam Araghi
2- Service Quality Performance of Conventional and Islamic Banks in Malaysia: An Empirical Study	Ros Aniza Mohd Shariff
3- Contextual Factors of Performance Measurement Design in Libyan Commercial Banks	Ismail Mohamed Elnihewi, Rapih Mohamed, Faudziah Hanim Fadzil
4- Determinants of Maqasid Shariah based Performance Measurement Practices : The Case of Malaysia Islamic Banks	Muslim Har Sani Muhamad, Muhammad Ahmar Ali

CRITICAL FACTORS IN COMPETATIVE ADVANTAGE OF ISLAMIC BANKING

Friend Al R., PhD
Maryam Araghi

Abstract

This research focuses on determining the impact of service quality, customer satisfaction, and loyalty programs on customers' loyalty in the Islamic banking sector of Malaysia. It is obvious that customers are important stakeholders in organizations, and their satisfaction is a priority to the management. Customer satisfaction has been a subject of great interest to organizations and researchers alike. In recent years, organizations are obliged to render additional services on top of their offers. The quality of service has become an aspect of customer satisfaction. It has been proven by some researchers that service quality is related to customer satisfaction. Others used service quality dimensions to evaluate service quality. Moreover, this study examined not only the relationship between service quality and its respective dimensions towards customer satisfaction and customer loyalty, but also the relationship between customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. The study showed distinctive results for the relationship between service quality dimensions and service quality/customer satisfaction, and also between customer satisfaction and customer loyalty.

Introduction

Islamic Banking (IB) is being regarded as one of the fastest growing industries globally and has contributed to the growth and sustainability of the Malaysian economy since its establishment in 1983 as it receives wide acceptance by both Muslims and non-Muslims alike (Iqbal and Molyneux, 2005). Islamic banks perform the same essential functions as banks do in the conventional system, except that the need for them to carry out their transactions in accordance with the rules and principles of Islam (Henry and Wilson, 2004; Iqbal and Mirakhor, 2007).

As one of the most important players in service industry today, Islamic banking is no longer regarded as a business entity striving only to fulfill the religious obligations of the Muslim community, but more significantly, as a business that is ineluctably in need for winning over customers whilst retaining the old ones (Wilson, 1995). This necessitates Islamic banks to really understand the perceptions of their customers towards them in terms of service quality and other patronage factors to secure customers' allegiance.

Therefore, Islamic banking can no longer be regarded as a business organization which is established to fulfill religious duties but what is more important, to be as competitive as possible side by side with the conventional system in alluring more customers and retain them. Inevitably, Islamic banks need to really understand the perceptions of their customers towards their business operations particularly their